

ing at tillering could give the crop protection against drought. Applying butachlor considerably reduced weed pressure.

References

- Chinoy JJ, Abraham PG, Pandya RB, Sesens OP, Dave IC. 1970. Effect of presowing treatment of *Triticum* seeds with ascorbic acid and sucrose on growth, development and yield characters. *Indian J. Plant Physiol.* 13:40-48.
- Mishra RD, Ahmed M. 1987. Manual on irrigation in agronomy. New Delhi (India): Oxford and IBH Publications.
- Mishra RK, Deshmukh MR, Pandkar VK, Tiwari KL. 1988. Efficacy of herbicides on direct-seeded rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *Pesticides* 22(4):10-12.
- Singh KN, Bhattacharyya HC. 1989. In: Direct-seeded rice: principles and practices. New Delhi (India): Oxford and IBH Publications. 166 p.

Table 2. Influence of seed treatment, water management, and weed control measures on weed dry matter (g m^{-2}).^a

Treatment	30 DAS		60 DAS		Harvest	
	Grass	Nongrass	Grass	Nongrass	Grass	Nongrass
Seed						
Normal	53	5	54	21	99 (8) ^b	45 (6)
Modified	43	7	48	15	101 (9)	99 (6)
CD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	5	ns	ns
Water management						
Rainfed	58	5	48	18	110 (9)	46 (5)
3 DII	44	5	53	20	99 (9)	57 (6)
6 DII	45	6	33	17	90 (8)	62 (6)
CD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Weed control						
Weedy check	68	6	66	16	140 (11)	23 (5)
Butachlor at 2 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	30	5	39	20	59 (6)	60 (7)
CD (0.05)	14	ns	9	5	3	ns

^aDAS = days after sowing, ns = not significant, DII = days of intermittent irrigation. ^bNumbers in parentheses are square-root-transformed values.

Effect of organic matter resources and inorganic fertilizers on yield and nutrient uptake in the rice-wheat cropping system

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A field experiment was conducted at the Fertilizer Research Station, Pura, Kanpur (India), during 1997-98 and 1998-99 to study the influence of organic sources along with inorganic fertilizers on the rice-wheat cropping system. The soil had the following characteristics: sand 51.8%, silt 25.6%, clay 21.3%, pH 7.9, electrical conductivity (EC, dS m⁻¹) 0.39, organic carbon 4.3 g kg⁻¹, available N 163.2 kg ha⁻¹, 7.1 kg P ha⁻¹, and 103.8 kg K ha⁻¹. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design consisting of five main-plot treatments: M₁—green manure (*Sesbania aculeata*), M₂—moong legume (*Phaseolus aureus*)

straw (5 t ha⁻¹), M₃—farmyard manure (5 t ha⁻¹), M₄—rice straw (5 t ha⁻¹), and M₅—weedy fallow; and five subplot treatments: F₀—control, F₁—50% N, F₂—50% NP, F₃—50% NPK, and F₄—100% NPK of the recommended dose (120 kg N, 26.4 kg P, and 49.8 kg K).

Adding different sources of organic matter significantly increased rice yield over weedy fallow. Treatments also differed significantly from each other. Maximum grain yield (3.7 t ha⁻¹) during 1997 and 1998 was obtained by M₁, followed by M₃ (3.6 t ha⁻¹), M₂ (3.5 t ha⁻¹), and M₄ (3.4 t ha⁻¹). Minimum grain yield was ob-

tained under the fallow treatment. Similarly, chemical fertilizers also significantly increased yield compared with the fertilizer control. A minimum yield of 2.0 t ha⁻¹ in the control increased to 3.2 t ha⁻¹ with F₁, to 3.6 t ha⁻¹ in F₂, to 4.0 t ha⁻¹ in F₃, and to 4.7 t ha⁻¹ in F₄ during 1997. A similar trend was recorded in 1998 (Table 1).

Different organic matter sources exhibited significant residual responses on grain and straw yield of the wheat crop. Maximum yield in the wheat crop was noted in the treatment with green manure, followed by farmyard manure, moong straw, and rice straw (Table 2).

Table 1. Effect of organic matter sources and fertilizer levels on grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of rice.

Main treatment	1997					Mean	1998					Mean
	Fertilizer level						Fertilizer level					
	F ₀	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄		F ₀	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	
M ₁ —Green manure (<i>Sesbania aculeata</i>)	2.2	3.4	3.8	4.2	5.0	3.7	2.3	3.4	3.8	4.2	5.0	3.7
M ₂ —Moong straw (<i>Phaseolus aureus</i>) (5 t ha ⁻¹)	2.0	3.2	3.5	4.0	4.7	3.5	2.0	3.2	3.6	4.0	4.8	3.5
M ₃ —Farmyard manure (5 t ha ⁻¹)	2.1	3.2	3.6	4.1	4.8	3.6	2.2	3.2	3.6	4.1	5.0	3.6
M ₄ —Rice straw (5 t ha ⁻¹)	1.9	3.1	3.5	3.9	4.7	3.4	2.0	3.1	3.5	4.0	4.7	3.4
M ₅ —Weedy fallow	1.8	2.9	3.4	3.8	4.5	3.3	1.8	3.0	3.5	3.8	4.6	3.3
Mean	2.0	3.2	3.6	4.0	4.7		2.1	3.2	3.6	4.0	4.8	
CD (0.05)	0.04											
	0.08											

Note: M compares M-means (averaged over F, subplot treatments) and F compares F-means (averaged over M, main-plot treatments).

Among organic matter sources, the total uptake of nutrient through the green manure treatment was maximum in relation to the total N, P, and K uptake. The contribution of the total uptake of N, P, and K was 17.4%, 14.9%, and 10.8% during 1997 and 17.4%, 14.8%, and 11.7% during 1998 (data for 1998 not shown) respectively, followed by the M₃ treatment during both years of the experiment (Table 3).

Table 2. Residual effect of organic matter sources applied to rice on yield (t ha⁻¹) of the succeeding wheat crop.

Treatment	1997-98		1998-99	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
M ₁	3.2	4.3	2.3	4.6
M ₂	3.1	4.1	3.2	4.1
M ₃	3.2	4.2	3.3	4.5
M ₄	3.0	4.0	3.1	4.3
M ₅	2.8	3.8	3.0	4.2
CD (0.05)	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.09

Table 3. Contribution of organic matter sources (% in parentheses) to total uptake of nutrients in rice during 1996-97.

Treatment	Total N uptake ^a (kg ha ⁻¹)	Total P uptake ^a (kg ha ⁻¹)	Total K uptake ^a (kg ha ⁻¹)
M ₁	76.39 (17.4)	13.42 (14.9)	88.89 (10.8)
M ₂	70.12 (7.8)	12.44 (6.5)	84.98 (5.8)
M ₃	73.19 (12.5)	12.92 (10.6)	87.02 (8.3)
M ₄	67.56 (3.9)	12.03 (3.0)	85.52 (2.7)
M ₅	65.05 (-)	11.68 (-)	80.32 (-)

^aGrain + straw.

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The leaf color chart (LCC) instructional video was produced to familiarize farmers and extension workers with the proper use of the leaf color chart, a new and affordable farming implement.

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